

MODERN METHODS AND FACTORS OF IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF SPEECH SKILLS FORMATION IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Abstract. In this article, the author considers one of the most urgent modern problems - methods and factors for improving the speech activity of teachers of the Russian language. The proposed principles, methods, techniques and teaching tools are aimed at increasing students' speech activity during the Russian language lesson, as well as preventing and eliminating their typical text errors.

Key words: Pedagogical speech, methods and factors, improvement, modern methodology, speech of teachers and students.

Pedagogical speech, first of all, should ensure effective listening of students in class. Perceived by the teacher's speech, the student performs many different operations: concretizes sound information in visual images, connects it with existing knowledge, experiences, understands, remembers, follows the logic of the teacher's presentation, develops his thoughts. This is a difficult task for the listening student, which should be taken into account when thinking through the content, pace, rhythm, logic, ease of the speech. Analyzing the importance of the tempo. Speech in school lessons showed that when the teacher violates the optimal speed of speech, students experience a sharp incompleteness and inaccuracy of perceived information, the amount of repeated incorrect information increases.

It is possible to show several modern methods of improving the methodology of formation of speech skills in teachers:

1) To develop self-control and speech culture, to form an attitude towards mastering correct, literary speech in all situations of oral communication:

- education of the need to learn and improve customs and speech culture;
- it is important to pay special attention to the correctness of speech (compliance with language standards - accent, pronunciation, word formation) and purity of speech.

Working with dictionaries helps a lot in this: clarification, difficulties in combining words. Turning to them in difficulty enriches the speech.

Look at the weaknesses in your speech (richness, clarity, consistency, fidelity) and work on changing them.

In solving business problems, in interpersonal communication, orient yourself to have full oral speech.

2) To develop self-control and expressive speech skills.

Skillful intonation, appropriateness of content, use of figurative means (epithets, metaphors), clarity of verbal imagery (excerpts from works of art, aphorisms)

When preparing a presentation, pay attention to the following:

- what thoughts should be evoked;
- what kind of mood to create;
- intonation and rhythm during performance.

Speak the speech, achieving the desired sound. Remember that the use of figurative language should be natural.

3) Development of communicative skills, abilities, social relations in the field of self-control and communication.

The condition of effective communicative behavior is the individual communication style of the teacher. It is important to study your social position in communication:

- my attitude towards people;
- Is the communication process interesting?
- Can I control my mood;
- Do people understand me?
- Am I attracted to myself?

The success of communicative behavior implies the development of a number of special abilities and skills in the future teacher:

- socio-perceptive (the ability to act in a partner, to understand his inner state);
- social imagination ability (put yourself in another's place, anticipate the reaction);
- self-control in communication, the ability to control mental state;
- voluntary influence, ability to offer.

4) development of general psychophysical personal characteristics that create the necessary conditions for the successful acquisition of speech skills and abilities.

- development of imagination (recreational and creative);
- associative and figurative memory, fantasy.

A necessary condition for the expressiveness of the teacher's speech is his mental view of the objects, events, and processes he is talking about.

In this case, the speech becomes emotional, lively, we draw pictures with the help of language. Such speech cannot be achieved by willpower. It is necessary to develop the ability to see and hear the world in colors and sounds, pictures, and to learn to convey visions in words.

A teacher's speech is an improvisation in the true sense of the word, an unprepared speech that occurs during direct communication with students, when circumstances require an immediate reaction from the teacher. And he answers - a detailed answer, a story, an instruction. In such situations, the responsibility of the teacher for the choice of words, forms of speech and the chosen tone of speech increases.

It is in speech behavior that the general culture and pedagogical culture of the teacher, the moral experience of his behavior, and his relations with students are manifested. Based on this, it is necessary to improve the method of formation of speech skills in teachers, based on their speech activity, as an example, students should develop their speech using modern methods and factors. There are three levels of this:

1. Reproductive activity of schoolchildren is the lowest level of independent thinking (working on a model, in which students apply the knowledge and skills they have acquired in a similar situation).

2. Partial research work - a high degree of independence of thinking (for example, when writing free dictation, when it is necessary to retell the text, it is manifested in showing some independence in choosing the content and means of expression).

3. Search activity - the highest level of independence of thinking (for example, it is done when writing an essay).

Based on these levels, I. Lerner offers the following classification of methods of improving the methodology of formation of speech skills in teachers:

- explanatory and illustrative method: they perceive, understand, remember what the teacher said;

- reproductive method: work is carried out by students according to the model given by the teacher under the guidance of the teacher;

- problem presentation: students are taught to independently analyze events; the teacher formulates a problem and reveals evidence-based solutions and methods of orientation in a new situation;

- partial-search method: a problem is set and by asking questions, the teacher involves students in the process of solving it based on evidence, helps

them find answers to questions, keywords are formed by the teacher and given to students.

- research method: students work in parallel with the teacher, acquire new knowledge and ways of obtaining it, solve the problem as a result of analyzing the material, justify the conclusion.

The classification of speech activity teaching methods from model work based on levels of independence of thought to partial research and full research is a system of improving students' speech activity and includes the following methods:

1) teaching repetition and analysis of these texts;

2) teaching to choose language tools according to a ready-made sample in connection with the change of these texts;

3) teaching creative use of language tools in connection with text creation.

Methods of using the first method: warning, explanation, selective dictation, writing a review, analysis of phonetic, grammatical, spelling and punctuation marks, making models of these expressions, leaving punctuation marks in the text unmarked, etc.

The methods of using the second method are restructured sentences for the purpose of mastering syntactic constructions and putting punctuation marks, replacing some syntactic constructions with others, replacing some words, phrases with others, etc.

The methods of using the third (creative) method include free dictation, presentation, writing an essay, preparing a review of a literary work, a performance, writing an article in a newspaper, an abstract, theses, a synopsis, etc.

Of course, the principles determine the content and methodology of teaching. Based on the teacher, there are the following principles with this order of the methodological system of the development of the student's speech activity:

1. General didactic: systematic, scientific, existing, educational nature of education;

2. Special: communication, taking into account the native language of students, helps to implement a complex, functional approach, as in the example of the teacher's speech.

Thus, the principle of consistency determines that students' knowledge, skills and competences are formed systematically, that is, in a certain order and sequence: the logical connection of each element of the educational material

with others, the teacher and prepares the student to master new material, with the next one building on the previous one. This didactic principle is based on a strict adherence to the educational sequence and a logically consistent approach to education.

So, teacher speech culture is a capacious and multifaceted concept. Language elements specially selected and used in a particular communication are, in fact, speech. The correctness of such a choice depends on the knowledge of the author of the speech, his ability to consciously choose and use the necessary language tools during communication. A teacher should work hard to form his pedagogical speech culture.

Rules of teacher's speech culture.

1. The teacher should speak quietly, but in such a way that everyone can hear him, so that the listening process does not cause significant stress for students.

2. The teacher must speak clearly.

3. The teacher should speak at a speed of about 120 words per minute.

4. It is important to be able to use pauses to achieve an expressive sound - logically and psychologically. Speech without logical pauses is illiterate, without psychological pauses colorless.

5. The teacher should speak with intonation, that is, he should be able to put logical accents, highlight the individual words that are important for the content of the spoken sentence.

6. The tone gives an individual color to the teacher's voice and can significantly affect the emotional state of students: it inspires, attracts, calms. However, the characteristics of the teacher's inner world, culture and spiritual wealth, confidence in the correctness of his words are probably the most important for the art of speech. S. L. Soloveitchik wrote: "Nowadays there is a lot of talk about the need to check the technical skills of the teacher, his voice, gesture, intonation. But more important is the teacher's moral character, communication style and behavior".

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